

SPECIFIC CHARACTERISTICS OF THE TRANSITION TO THE CREDIT-MODULE SYSTEM IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: *This article describes the credit-modular system, the stages of its emergence and development, its unique features, significance, opportunities and advantages, as well as the features of the implementation of this system in higher education in Uzbekistan.*

Key words: *education, credit, module, process, assessment, potential, contract, conversion, rating, self-study, scientific program.*

Today, in the field of education, as in all areas of the world, innovations, modern methods of teaching and assessment are being introduced. One such innovation is the credit-module system, which is used in almost all European countries.

On October 8, 2019, the head of our state signed the Decree "On approval of the concept of development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030". In this important programmatic document, "at least 10 higher education institutions in the republic are ranked by internationally recognized organizations (Quacquarelli Symonds World University Rankings, Times Higher Education or Academic Ranking of World Universities) as higher education institutions in the first 1000 places." to be included in the list and to gradually transfer the educational process to the credit-module system in higher education institutions.

[1]

Also, by 2030, 85 percent of all higher education institutions (HEIs) in the republic, including 33 higher education institutions in the 2020/2021 academic year, will be transferred to the credit-module system. was asked.

The main goal of the transition to this system is to increase the scientific potential of higher education institutions, to provide them with highly qualified professors and teachers. - was determined to implement a number of education development activities of the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Republican Council of Higher Education at the expense of extra-budgetary funds from contract training.

In particular, the internship and professional development of professors and teachers in prestigious foreign higher education organizations and scientific institutions with the signing of a contract that provides for 3 years of work at a higher education institution, and 5 years of work at a higher education institution implementation of expenses related to training of teachers on the basis of doctoral programs of prestigious foreign higher education organizations and scientific institutions, material and technical support of state educational and research institutions operating under the higher educational institution These include tasks such as allocating necessary funds for base strengthening, construction, current and capital repair, reconstruction and equipment works.

Based on the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 824 of December 31, 2020 "On measures to improve the system related to the organization of the educational process in higher education institutions" "In higher education institutions "Regulation on the procedure for introducing the credit-module system into the educational process" was developed. and Accumulation System — ECTS) determines the procedure for introducing the credit-module system of education. Also, the main concepts of the credit-module system, the structure of the educational program, planning the educational process, monitoring and ensuring the quality of education, academic mobility and recognition of credits, evaluation, conversion of grades, in the credit-module system organization

of registration service and the mechanisms of student suspension, reinstatement, transfer from course to course are also regulated on the basis of this Regulation. In addition, this Regulation establishes the gradual introduction of the credit-module system into the educational process in higher education institutions, according to which, starting from the 2020-2021 academic year until 2030, all higher education institutions in our Republic It is envisaged that educational institutions will fully transition to the credit-module system. [2]

The credit-module system is a process of educational organization and is an evaluation model based on a set of module technologies of education and a credit measure. Carrying it out as a whole is a complex and systematic process. In the principle of credit module, special importance is attached to the issues of ensuring independent work of students and evaluating students' knowledge based on rating.

The following are recognized as the main tasks of the credit module system:

- organization of educational processes on the basis of modules;
- determining the value of one subject, course (credit);
- assessment of students' knowledge based on the rating score;
- to enable students to create their own study plans individually;
- increasing the share of independent education in the educational process;
- the convenience of educational programs and the ability to change based on the demand for a specialist in the labor market.

Let's briefly touch on the essence of the module and credit concepts here.

A module is a part of the curriculum in which several subjects and courses are studied. It is a set of several subjects aimed at students to acquire certain knowledge and skills, to have the potential for analytical and logical observation. In this, the teacher organizes the educational process, gives live, video and audio lectures, coordinates and monitors the student's activities. The student learns the subject independently and completes the assigned tasks.

In the credit-module system, the educational process consists of 2-3 modules per semester. The subjects included in the module are formed from easy to complex,

from theoretical-methodical subjects to applied subjects and based on the principle of logical complementarity. In order for a student to become a specialist, it is necessary to acquire not only information, but also the ability to process it and put it into practice.

A credit is a unit of measurement of the educational load (time) spent by a student to study and master subjects in a particular educational direction or program (course). Credit is the minimum amount of time allocated for a student to study independently and in the classroom, usually for one week. Credit is given to the student after completing the assigned tasks in a certain subject and successfully passing the final exam.

Each student must accumulate credits in order to obtain a diploma in the field and specialty of his choice in the future. The accumulated credit will serve the student to improve his qualifications or receive additional higher education throughout his life. In economic terms, accumulated credit becomes a student's academic "asset". [3] Credit technology gives students the right to choose elective subjects included in the working curriculum, thereby directly participating in the formation of an individual curriculum. They are given the freedom to choose not only subjects, but also professors and teachers. Giving students the opportunity to choose subjects is a positive thing. It is also considered to be a unique value indicator of the evaluation of educational processes.

A credit is a unit of measurement of the educational load mastered by a student in a specific subject according to the results of education. Credit accumulation is the accumulation of credit units provided as a result of mastering educational elements and achieving other achievements.

The credit-hour system first appeared and developed in the United States. In 1968, the famous figure of American education, Charles Eliot, president of Harvard University, introduced the concept of "credit hour", and in 1870-80, the amount of academic work measured in credit hours was introduced. In 1892, the second stage of the development of the "credit-hour" system was started. In order to improve the

"college-school" connection and standardize the curriculum, the concept of "credit" was introduced in secondary schools and colleges by the US National Education Committee. Schools have switched to a credit system to assess the content of bachelor's, master's and doctoral programs.

The implementation of this system in higher education will increase the quality of teaching, ensure transparency, eliminate corruption, reveal the true knowledge of the learner, and create a foundation for the student to study and work independently. However, it should not be forgotten that when moving to a new system, the level of potential of students and professors, their adaptability to innovation, the science programs and curricula developed by educational institutions, the educational literature being created, it is necessary to gradually adapt the textbooks and manuals to the conditions set before us by this system. The main task before us is not to introduce foreign experience in a hasty manner, but to bring the quality of higher education, the knowledge and skills of our students, and the scientific potential of our professors and teachers on par with world standards and developed countries.

List of used literature:

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 8, 2019 No. PF-5847 "On approval of the concept of development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030".

2. Resolution No. 824 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 31, 2020 "On measures to improve the system related to the organization of the educational process in higher education institutions."

3. Usmanov B.Sh., Habibullayev R.A. Organization of the educational process in higher educational institutions in the credit-module system. Study guide. - Tashkent, TKTI, 2020. - Page 120.